

CAUSES OF INFLATION IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN AND WAYS TO ELIMINATE IT

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Abstract. *This article describes inflation, its nature, types, internal and external factors that create conditions for the rise of inflation in the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as its analysis and reasons. Inflation is a key indicator of a country's economic health and reflects the increase in the general level of prices over time. Understanding the causes and effects of inflation is important for policymakers and individuals alike. This article describes the analysis of inflation processes in the Republic of Uzbekistan in detail and the set of measures to eliminate them.*

Keywords: *inflation process, economic indicators, hyperinflation, economic instability, economic uncertainty, monetary policy, money supply, inflationary risks, budget deficit.*

It is known that the level of inflation in Uzbekistan has been changing over the past few decades. In the 1990s, after gaining independence from the Soviet Union, the country faced a period of hyperinflation due to rapid economic transition. However, since the beginning of the 2000s, Uzbekistan has made great efforts to stabilize its economy and achieve a stable level of inflation. The expansion of the money supply by the Central Bank is one of the main causes of inflation. The Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan plays a decisive role in the management of money supply in Uzbekistan. If the bank overextends money supply or does not regulate it effectively, this can lead to inflationary pressures. Changes in the dynamics of supply and demand can also contribute to inflation. For example, supply shocks, such as disruptions in the availability of essential goods or materials, can cause prices to rise. In addition, changes in demand due to factors such as population growth or changes in consumer preferences can affect inflation.

The presence of banknotes and coins in circulation is one of the economic categories that cause inflation. The term "inflation" is derived from the Latin word "inflation" which means "inflated", "exaggerated", "increased". The economic essence of inflation means a decrease in the purchasing power of cash in circulation and an increase in the price of goods and services. From the middle of the 19th century, until it was used by economists as an economic term, it was used in medicine to describe a malignant tumor. History has shown that this word is indeed dangerous in every way. Because inflation is not only an increase in the price of goods and services in some individual markets, it is a dangerous phenomenon for the economy as a whole. The economic meaning of the word inflation means issuing a lot of money compared to the goods in circulation and their prices. If we pay attention to history, the increase in other expenses due to war and other disasters is inextricably linked with inflation. For example, strong inflation was manifested in England at the beginning of the 19th century during the war with Napoleon, in France - during the French Revolution, and in Russia in the middle of the 19th century. Very high inflation in Germany occurred in 1923, when the money in circulation reached 496 quintillion marks and the currency depreciated a trillion times.

These historical examples show that inflation is not a current process, but a historical process. Inflation and its development may have certain characteristics in a particular country.

Structural factors such as inefficient production systems, distribution networks and market monopolies can also affect the inflation rate. Inefficiencies in the economy can put upward pressure on prices, especially if production costs are high or barriers to competition exist. In the conditions of inflation, people and businessmen are worried about the devaluation of money and try to get rid of cash, plastic cards and deposits on demand as soon as possible. This phenomenon is usually called money flight. As a result, the speed of circulation of currency units increases, which has the effect of increasing the money supply. In addition, in many cases, sellers include tomorrow's inflation in today's price of goods, that is, they only agree to sell their products at a higher price than they actually are. The fear of inflation is primarily due to the fact that the population and business do not believe that the state can curb inflation.

Therefore, anti-inflation fight should be firm, consistent and open. Only then will the population and business give up their worries about inflation, which will be an important factor in the fight against price increases. When inflation rises faster than wages, it reduces people's purchasing power. This can lead to a decrease in the living standards of the population and households, especially those with fixed incomes or those with a weak socio-economic status. Persistent inflation can create economic uncertainty, which makes it difficult for enterprises to plan and invest.

High inflation rates can disrupt the functioning of markets and distort the allocation of resources. In addition, inflation reduces the value of savings, discourages investment, and leads to economic instability. Inflation can increase income inequality because it affects low-income individuals more severely, and increases in the cost of essential goods and services disproportionately affect the weaker sections of society, that makes it difficult for them to have basic needs. The government of Uzbekistan has implemented a number of measures to effectively manage inflation. These include:

-Monetary policy:

The Central Bank of Uzbekistan conducts a reasonable monetary and credit policy in order to maintain price stability. It actively monitors money supply growth, interest rates, and exchange rate movements to regulate inflationary pressures.

-Tax policy:

The government manages its expenses and income responsibly and implements tax discipline. Maintaining a sustainable budget deficit will help reduce inflationary pressures from excess government spending.

-Structural reforms:

Important reforms have been implemented in Uzbekistan to eliminate inflationary risks arising from structural factors. These reforms are aimed at improving the efficiency of production systems, developing competition, and ensuring a stable and well-regulated business environment. Inflation is one of the most important issues in the economy. Because inflation means that money will depreciate. This all-round escalation of inflation will lead to the emergence of social and economic contradictions in the country. All economic communications are adjusted for inflation. The President Sh. Mirziyoyev in his address to Oliy Majlis of December 28, 2018 said: "...We must ensure macroeconomic stability and high growth rates. First of all, it is impossible to achieve macroeconomic stability without curbing inflation". Therefore, the state develops measures to prevent inflation. The main forms of combating inflation are: anti-inflationary policy and monetary

reform. Today, the rate of inflation is expected to rise sharply in our country, and countermeasures are being considered. Acceleration of inflation creates a number of difficulties.

These include a decline in interest in manufacturing and investment. This is the third priority direction of the Action Strategy. Reforms in the further development of the economy, expansion of foreign economic relations, introduction of modern technologies for the production of products and materials intended for export, development of entrepreneurship and increase of investment attractiveness for foreign investors are a big obstacle. In addition to this, the high rate of inflation disrupts the normal functioning of financial markets.

What interest rate to lend and borrow, how much return you should expect from securities - all this will depend on the expected rate of inflation. This has a very unpleasant effect on the development of the economy. Internal factors of inflation are divided into types related to monetary policy and economic activity.

Factors related to economic activity are a violation of balance in the economy allowing monopolies in production, cyclical development of the economy, imbalance in investment, monopolies of the state in organizing prices, wrong credit policy, and other money-related factors include crises in the field of public finances, the state's budget deficit, the growth of public debts, money emission, violations of the law of money circulation, allowing automaticity in lending, etc. The analysis of inflation processes in the Republic of Uzbekistan reveals several main points. First, Uzbekistan has seen a significant increase in inflation rates in recent years, with factors such as supply disruptions, demand pressures, and exchange rate depreciation contributing to price increases. This had various effects on the economy, businesses and individuals.

High inflation in Uzbekistan has created challenges for businesses, making it difficult for them to plan for the future and invest with confidence. In addition, inflation has led to a redistribution of income, which has affected different sections of the population in a unique way. Those with fixed incomes have struggled to cope with rising prices, while those with variable incomes or assets have fared relatively better.

Inflation also affected the country's international competitiveness. If the rate of inflation in Uzbekistan remains significantly higher than that of other countries, this could reduce the competitiveness of exports and increase the cost of imports, potentially affecting the trade balance. The fear of inflation is primarily due to the fact that the population and business do not believe that the government can control inflation. If we do not control inflation, the liberalization of the financial sector and the foreign exchange market will lead to the transfer of financial resources from production to the hands of speculators, which will have a negative impact on investment and production and employment growth.

Uzbekistan has encountered significant difficulties in achieving its major macroeconomic objectives in recent times. The International Monetary Fund predicts that Uzbekistan will conclude 2023 with an inflation rate of 11.8%. Several key factors have contributed to the failure to reduce the inflation rate.

Unanticipated External Factors:

Unforeseen events beyond Uzbekistan's control have significantly impacted the deviation of inflation from the set indicators. The COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 and the subsequent global economic downturn, along with conflicts among major trading partners in 2022, have had a negative effect on Uzbekistan's efforts to stabilize the inflation rate.

Import-Export Imbalance:

Another critical factor is the significant trade imbalance between imports and exports in Uzbekistan. According to the 2022 data, imports exceeded exports by 1.5 times, amounting to \$30.7 billion. This imbalance results in an increased cost of raw materials acquired from foreign sources, leading to higher production expenses in Uzbekistan and ultimately causing a hike in the prices of goods and services.

Currency Depreciation:

Uzbekistan's currency has undergone a major devaluation in comparison to other Central Asian countries. According to the International Monetary Fund, by 2022, the Uzbekistan's currency decreased by 750 points, whereas Kazakhstan's decreased by 300 points and Tajikistan's – by 550 points.

Informal Economy:

A significant portion, amounting to 27.2%, of Uzbekistan's economy is active within the informal sector. Such a reality suggests that a notable volume of economic activity remains untaxed and income undisclosed in official paperwork.

Potential Solutions:

Uzbekistan faces various challenges in addressing high inflation, but there are many feasible opportunities to combat it.

Monetary and Fiscal Policy:

Uzbekistan can utilize a combination of monetary and fiscal measures to stabilize prices and address inflation. Achieving a delicate equilibrium between managing inflation and promoting economic growth is pivotal, as each goal carries its own set of challenges.

Currency and Credit Policy:

Prudent management of exchange rates and credit policies is crucial to alleviate inflationary pressures resulting from currency depreciation and increasing production costs.

Inflation targeting:

In order to ensure effective monetary policy in Uzbekistan, it is recommended to continue utilizing inflation targeting methods. This involves establishing clear and specific inflation targets and employing various strategies to achieve them.

Market-based reforms:

Promoting free-market reforms and minimizing government intervention in the economy is vital for efficient and sustainable growth. However, it is crucial to undertake these reforms cautiously, ensuring that they do not have any destabilizing effects.

Achieving and sustaining inflation targets is a challenging process, influenced by various domestic and global factors. Uzbekistan, like other nations, is grappling with challenges in this regard.

Various policy measures and strategies exist to combat high inflation, but they can have negative consequences that warrant careful consideration. Striking a balance between controlling inflation and promoting economic growth is crucial. In sum, implementing monetary and credit, fiscal, and public administration reforms will be essential to decrease inflation and ensure stable economic development in Uzbekistan.

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